

HISTORICAL-THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIO-CULTURAL PROCESSES ON THEATRICAL ART

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Abstract: This article examines the historical and theoretical foundations of the influence of socio-cultural processes on theatrical art and provides analytical conclusions.

Keywords: Theatrical art, socio-cultural processes, performance, jadid, culture, ideology, troupe, integration.

ИСТОРИКО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВЛИЯНИЯ СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ НА ТЕАТРАЛЬНОЕ ИСКУССТВО

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены историко-теоретические основы влияния социокультурных процессов на театральное искусство и даны аналитические выводы.

Ключевые слова: Театральное искусство, социокультурные процессы, спектакль, Джадид, культура, идеология, труппа, интеграция.

INTRODUCTION

In the socio-cultural, ideological processes taking place in foreign countries, the awareness of the identity of peoples, nationalities, the absorption of the national spirit into citizens is of particular importance. Today, the widespread spread of the culture of each nation presupposes the need to seriously focus on the issues of promoting the art of the National Theater, preserving and developing its traditions. This in turn indicates that it is relevant to study the history, specific culture and art of the peoples of the world in harmony with universal values.

The enlighteners took and studied performances performed by Russian, Azerbaijani, tatar touring troupes that entered Turkestan, and a column of European-specific theatrical art was created. “Padarkush”, “the unfortunate groom”, “the wedding”, “Juvonmarg”, “Mazluma the wife”, “Old School, New School”, staged by the exponents of speed, are all aimed at revealing the everyday life of the people. Their main content was to instill in the public consciousness the importance of a new education, to criticize the negative consequences caused by ignorance in society.

MAIN PART

The influence of oral dramaturgy, Folk field theater traditions, Heroes is clearly felt in the works in which the Jadid intelligentsia created a special feature of stage plays (especially comic plays). At the same time, one can see that in the stage interpretations of jadid dramas and comedies, the aspiration for European-type theater is felt. Performances prepared for the stage began to be shown in the theater building or on special stages.

The socio-political, cultural processes of any society are sealed in documents dating back to their time, official sources, memoirs, memories of those who lived in that time. Their study and analysis provides an opportunity to see and draw conclusions and further understand the essence of changes in the dominant ideology, social life and culture of the time, the factors that influenced it.

The October 1917 coup marked a turning point in the socio-political and cultural life of the territories, including Turkestan, a colony of the Russian Empire. Progressive intellectuals in the country actively moved towards the development of the country. Cultural issues in this process

also did not go unnoticed by them. The theater sphere, an integral link in culture, came to the fore with the establishment of the Soviet system as an important piece of propaganda work in a new way. The pre-existing Performing Arts in the country began to take shape and modernize as a theater with the say-movement of the jadids.

In Particular, T. Tursunov's work "history of the Uzbek theater of the 20th century" reveals the Uzbek traditional theater, its manifestations, the role of jadids in the creation of the new Uzbek Theater in the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries, the establishment of the Soviet government and the nationalization of theatrical art through the path of creativity of actors.¹

About the jadidism movement as well as Uzbek jadid drama, art scholar Sh.Rizayev also cites important data in his research.² The scientist believes that the formation of Uzbek jadid drama and theater was primarily due to the need and necessity of social life. In 1911, Makhmudhaja Behbudi wrote "3 curtains- 4 landscapes-National, First tragedy" under the title "padarkush or holi of the child who did not read". This work was published in Samarkand in 1913 as a separate book. The announcement of the play "Padarkush" was not an ahmatiyya phenomenon for the intellectuals of Behbudiy or the city of Samarkand, but an impetus for the further revitalization of socio-cultural life in all of Turkestan, for new-New Enlightenment communities to come to the square on the basis of theater amateurs.

It is no secret that special importance is attached to the development of literature and art, along with all aspects of our cultural and educational life in our country, the reforms carried out in these areas serve to raise the morale, artistic thinking of our people. After all, the promotion of noble ideas, National and universal values among society, the upbringing of the nation, especially the younger generation, these two tools occupy an important place in their maturation as a true person.

Among the types of art, the theater is distinguished by its lively nature, impressiveness, direct influence on the human psyche, consciousness, a clear-bright personification of a particular event-event before the eyes of the viewer, and other features.³ "An intimate connection between the stage and the audience hall, dialogue is formed that spiritually enriches, spiritually enriches, entertain both the performers and the audience. That is, double influence is generated" as well as theater as a social pulpit, reflecting the worldview of many, it can react to changes in society, ideological processes, and thus serve the formation of social thought.

In recent years, great attention has been paid to objectively studying the historical roots of Uzbek theatrical art in Uzbekistan, introducing it to the world, improving the field on the basis of modern requirements. This demonstrates the importance of preserving the Uzbek tradition of theatre arts, analyzing it from a historical point of view. Also, on December 22, 2023, at the expanded meeting of the Republican Council of spirituality and enlightenment, held under the leadership of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it was noted that "it is necessary to develop a separate program document on the development of our national idea, which will serve as a methodological basis for the field of spirituality and culture."⁴

¹ Tursunov T. Uzbek theatre history of the 20th century. – Toshkent, 2010. – 568 p.

² Sh.Rizayev. "Jadid dramasi"//Mas'ul muharrir N.Karimov/. – T.: Sharq, 1997. – 35-b.

³ Istiqlol va milliy teatr (to'plam) – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2002.

⁴ President: spirituality should move ahead of other areas, become a new force, a new movement/
https://president.uz/uz/rasmiy_sayti 2023.

CONCLUSION

In particular, the development of a program for the development of theatrical art was envisaged in it such tasks as creative commissioning for the best plays, improving the skills of creative and supporting staff in foreign theaters, establishing an award named after Mannon Uyghur to support young directors. One day of the month for employees of enterprises and institutions was designated “Theater Day”.

List of literature used:

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